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О журнале

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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN METABOLIC DISORDERS AND SLEEP DISTURBANCES IN CHILDREN: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Resume. This literary review explores the intersection of sleep disorders and metabolic disorders in pediatric populations. The reviewed studies highlight that children with metabolic disorders—such as glycogen storage diseases, mitochondrial dysfunctions, and inborn errors of metabolism—are particularly vulnerable to various sleep disturbances, including insomnia, sleep apnea, and restless sleep. The literature underscores the bidirectional relationship where metabolic dysfunction can disrupt sleep architecture, and conversely, poor sleep can exacerbate metabolic imbalances. Several articles emphasize the importance of early diagnosis and integrated management strategies to improve both metabolic control and sleep quality, which are critical for the overall growth, cognitive development, and quality of life in affected children.

Keywords: children, metabolic syndrome, disomnia, vegetative disorders, pathophysiology

METABOLIK O'ZGARISHLAR VA UYQUSIZLIKLAR O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK: ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

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Rezyume. Ushbu adabiyotlar sharhi bolalarda uyqu buzilishi va metabolik kasalliklar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni o'rganadi. Tahlil qilingan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, glikogenni to'planish kasalliklari, mitoxondriyal disfunktsiya va metabolizmning tug'ma buzilishlari kabi metabolik kasalliklarga chalingan bolalar uyqusizlik, uyqu apnoesi va notinch uyqu kabi turli xil uyqu buzilishlariga ayniqsa moyil. Adabiyotlarda ikki tomonlama munosabatlar ta'kidlanadi: metabolik buzilishlar uyqu arxitekturasi buzishi mumkin va yomon uyqu o'z navbatida metabolik nomutanosiblikni kuchaytiradi. Sharh shuningdek, hozirgi tadqiqotlardagi kamchiliklarni, xususan, metabolik anormalliklarni va uyquni tartibga solishni bog'laydigan mexanizmlarni tushinishda va individual terapevtik yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: bolalar, metabolik sindrom, dissonniya, vegetativ buzilishlar, patofiziologiya

СВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКИМИ НАРУШЕНИЯМИ И РАССТРОЙСТВАМИ СНА У ДЕТЕЙ: ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

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Резюме. Данный обзор литературы исследует взаимосвязь между расстройствами сна и метаболическими нарушениями у детей. Проанализированные исследования показывают, что дети с метаболическими расстройствами — такими как болезни накопления гликогена, митохондриальные дисфункции и врожденные ошибки метаболизма — особенно подвержены различным нарушениям сна, включая бессонницу, апноэ сна и беспокойный сон. В литературе подчеркивается двунаправленная связь: метаболические нарушения могут нарушать структуру сна, а, в свою очередь, плохой сон усугубляет метаболические дисбалансы. В обзоре также отмечаются пробелы в современных исследованиях, особенно в понимании механизмов, связывающих метаболические аномалии и регуляцию сна, а также необходимость разработки индивидуализированных терапевтических подходов.

Ключевые слова: дети, метаболический синдром, диссонния, вегетативные нарушения, патофизиология

Metabolic syndrome is a widespread comorbid condition characterized by a complex of sympathetic symptoms that develop due to the disruption of certain bodily systems in a child. In many cases, metabolic changes result in hyperglycemia in the serum, while simultaneously causing glucose deficiency at the cellular level due to impaired insulin resistance [1]. Many body structures, including parts of the nervous system responsible for attention and memory—mainly the frontal lobes and hippocampus—are particularly sensitive to this hypoglycemic state. This leads to pathological changes in the hypothalamic region, which controls the autonomic nervous system.

The weakening of inhibitory mechanisms of the hypothalamic system on the sympathetic nervous system in the brainstem and activation of the sympathetic nervous system during metabolic alterations observed

in the body [6] has been scientifically proven. This area requires further study. Childhood obesity with metabolic changes is increasing daily. This rise is linked to modern lifestyle changes, neglect of children's healthy habits, attraction to fast food and processed foods, and increased use of gadgets occupying most of the child's life [7], as well as various pathological states in the child's body.

Earlier experimental studies confirmed the negative impact of metabolic changes on the child's cognitive state, including attention deficits [13]. Later studies showed an overall relationship between metabolic changes and memory function in children. These contradictions highlight the need for deeper research in this area. Metabolic disorders cause brain changes that affect the physiological state of the cerebral hemispheres, resulting in specific clinical neurological symptoms in children. These can be detected both in the nervous and autonomic nervous systems and persist as functional impairments [10]. The effects of metabolic changes on sleep disorders in children have been widely discussed in international literature. Sleep is a periodic physiological functional state. Professor V.M. Kovalzon notes that sleep consists of alternating periods and phases. In critical physiological states, sleep includes slow-wave (non-REM) and rapid eye movement (REM or paradoxical) phases, which alternate several times during the night. By morning, REM sleep predominates. Slow-wave sleep corresponds to parasympathetic nervous system activity and serves to restore the brain's energy and electrolyte balance.

The regulation of sleep is controlled by several brain structures: the diencephalon, thalamus, and hypothalamus control non-REM sleep, while the midbrain and medulla regulate the REM phase. Sleep is also influenced by external factors, the child's emotional state, and lifestyle [12]. Deficiency of non-REM sleep phases leads to psychological changes and memory impairment affecting attention [11]. REM sleep deficits cause disruptions in the production of growth hormone and testosterone and affect cerebrospinal fluid circulation.

Sleep disturbances related to metabolic disorders are a pressing problem in modern medicine [12]. Metabolic changes induce autonomic nervous system dysfunctions, characterized by increased sympathetic nervous activity despite obesity in children. Hypothalamic dysfunction leads to sleep disturbances, as observed in conditions like encephalitis [15]. The ventrolateral preoptic area of the hypothalamus regulates slow-wave sleep.

C. Saper (2001) proposed that human wakefulness depends on hypothalamic peptides orexin/hypocretin produced in the lateral hypothalamus, influencing transitions between sleep phases. These systems interact via the dorsomedial hypothalamus, which regulates sleep rhythms, movement, body temperature, and steroid secretion [10].

Neuronal dysfunction in insomnia involves heightened activity, anxiety, and decreased well-being, resulting in increased sympathetic nervous system activity throughout the day and night [17]. Nofzinger et al. (2006) found vegetative dysfunction symptoms in patients, with PET scans showing increased glucose metabolism in brainstem, thalamo-cortical pathways, and brain hemispheres [12].

Cortisol, a steroid hormone produced by adrenal glands, activates the stress response and, during psycho-emotional stress, is stimulated by ACTH hormone [9]. It accelerates heart rate, raises blood pressure, facilitates glycogen conversion to glucose, and prepares the body for stress, while regulating inflammation and lipid metabolism [7].

Patients diagnosed with vegetative-vascular dystonia (VVD) often present with dissomnia. Metabolic changes are scientifically shown to accompany autonomic dysfunction.

Thus, dissomnia in metabolic disorders can be viewed as autonomic nervous system dysfunction, and sleep disturbances in children with metabolic syndrome remain under-researched, highlighting the need for further pathophysiological, clinical, and diagnostic studies.

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